

Socio-Economic Status Of Female Agricultural Labours In Sangli District : Geographical Analysis

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Abstract:

Agriculture plays a vital role as the backbone of a nation's economy. Rural sectors of India completely depend upon agriculture as their basic livelihood. Here Women's agricultural labour force plays the most important contribution to the farming of the nation. Women agricultural labourers are socially and financially the poorest section of society. Unemployment, illiteracy, under nutrition, dual responsibility, shortage of wage, lack of access to resources, indecisive behaviour, and lack of efficiency in handling technology are major drawbacks of women agricultural labourers which create major hindrances in their working conditions. In most of the developing societies, it is common to find a large number of poor people who are living out with a subsistence level of income could not able to come out of the grip of poverty. A multitude of factors— economic and non-economic are responsible for the problem of poverty. Any discussion on the problem of poverty in the Indian context is incomplete without references to landless agricultural workers, who are facing several problems on many fronts, are inevitably more vulnerable to the malice of unemployment, inequality and poverty. Faced with the seasonal nature of employment along with their poor resource capacity, they are forced to work very hard to make a decent life. In most cases, a typical Indian agricultural labour's households contain more than one earning member and more dependent members. The need for women members of the Indian agricultural labourer's family to go in work is forced because of inadequate employment opportunities and not that much.

Keywords: - Socio-economic status, working condition female agricultural labourer

Introduction:-

Agriculture is our country's backbone and provides a basic livelihood to the rural economy. Rural India completely depends upon farming for their employment and basic livelihood. In India, women in agriculture labour comprise about 2/3rd of the total labour force. The women agricultural labourers still face several challenges and hurdles but are still majorly responsible for farm production and home maintenance. Dave (2012) conducted the study on women workers engaged in unorganized sector to know about the socioeconomic background, working conditions, wage rates, living conditions of women workers engaged in unorganized sectors like construction, domestic and agriculture in three districts of Haryana. She concluded that women labourers face problems like excessive work burden, wage discrimination, exploitation, untimely wage payment, seasonal unemployment, job insecurity, health problems. Lal and Khurana (2011) discussed about multidimensional roles and obstacles faced by women in terms of employment, wages, dual responsibility, education level. Though women share is very high in agricultural and they are

spending more hours for work on farm than men still they are paid less than males for the same work. Women are undervalued because of the predetermined notion that women's basic role is of homemaker.

Objectives:

- 1) To analysis socio- economic status of female agricultural labours in atpadi tahsil
- 2) To syudy the working condition of female agricultural laborers

Sources Of Data:

The present study was based on the primary as well as secondary data. Primary data are collected through field work and secondary data are obtained with help of unpublished and published literature concerned with the topic.

Research Design: Descriptive as well as empirical research design is adopted for the present study.

Study Area:

Dighanchi village is located in Atpadi tahsil of sangli district it belong s to desh or western maharashtra .

Location Map

Methodology of study

Women in Dighanchi village are of distinct types. Some women workers are members of family forms a unit. Some women work as independent labours and undertake different activities independently. This independent labours coming from different social divisions are specific in that independent living is virtue. The economic status of groups of individuals can be studied by household survey. The researcher asks the question method for collecting information of working women labour. The study consists of simple random method was used for the study. There were 40 sample respondents of the women agriculture labours

Sources of Data:

The present study was based on the primary as well as secondary data were selected by using convenient sampling method

Data Processing:

Table no.1.1. Distribution of the respondents according to their Age-Group

Sr.no	Age group	Respondents	percentages
1	18-30	15	37.5
2	31-45	20	50
3	46-60	5	12.5
4	Above 60	-	-
	Total	40	100

Source Based on Field survey

The tabale represent a meajority50 percentof the respondents belong to the age group 31-45,followed by 37.5 percent of the respondents who belong to

The quantifiable data were coded and codebook was prepared. The coded data were entered into the computer and have been processed with the help of SPSS software, and made ready for interpretation. The computer generated out-put is used for tabulation, analysis and interpretation

Statistical Techniques:

Descriptive statistics is used. Single frequency tables are used for data analysis and interpretation:

Socio-Economic Profile Of Female Agricultural Labourers

Results and Discussions

Age of Respondents

Let us now look at the age of the respondents. The distribution of the respondents according to the age group categories to which they belong at present has been presented in the table no.1.1 below

the age-group of 18-30, another 12.5percent of the respondents belong to age-group of 46-60,

The detailed analysis of the socio-economic condition of the women agricultural labours and also their work efficiency has been indicated in table-1

Table-1.2: Caste Groups of the Households

Sr.no .	Cast group	No .of households	Percentages
1.	Sc /ST	25	62.5
2.	Obc	13	32.5
3.	Open	2	5
4.	Others	-	-
	Total	40	100

Source Based on field survey

In the above table shows that SC and ST households were 62.5 per cent and OBC was 32.5 per cent and opens were 2 per cent. The majority group of households were belongs to SC/ST.

Table 1.3 religion group

Sr.no	Religion Groups	N0 of respondent	Percentages
1.	Hindu	38	95
2.	Muslim	02	5
	Total	40	100

Source Based Field survey

The tabale 1.2presents ,majority found to belong to a 95 percent respondent were hindu ,only 5 percent found to muslim

Educational Status

Religion Groups of the respodents

Let us now look at the religious background of the respondents of the present study. The data regarding the religious background of the respondents are presented in the table no.1.2 below.

Your educational status determines your entry into the occupation. Therefore in a present study, respondent's educational status has been assessed. Educational status of the respondents is presented in table no.1.3below

Table no.1.4 Educational Status of Respondents

Sr.no	Education level	Respondents	Percentages
1	below 7 th	20	50
2	Up to 10 th	5	12.5
3	Up to 12 th	2	5
4	Illiterate	13	32.5
	Total	40	100

Source Based on Field survey

The tabale 1.4, presented in the indicates that 50 percent of the respondents were found to be educated only below 7th std, another 32.5 percent respondents were found to be illiterate and 12.5 percent of the respondents were found to be educated up to 10th std. Only 5 percent of the respondents were found to be educated up to 12th std. In the present study, it clearly reveals that an overwhelming majority (79 percent Illiterate, up to

7th) of the respondents were found to be less educated or illiterate which forced her to do agricultural work where no skill is required.

Type of Family

It is important to understand the family structure of the respondents while studying women labourers in agricultural sector. The data regarding the kind of family structure were collected in the present study and it is presented in the table no.1.4 below

Tabale 1.5 Family structure

Sr. No	Types	Respondents	Percentages
1	Joint	25	62.5
2	Nuclear	15	37.5
	Total	40	100

Source Based on field survey

The tabale show the family structure of the respondent,62.5 percent respondenents were found to joint family remaining 37.5 percent were found to nuclear family

Marital Status

Let us now look at the marital status of the respondents. The data regarding the marital status of the respondents are presented in the table no.1.5 below.

Table no.1.6. Distribution of Respondents According to Their Marital Status

Sr.no	Marital status	Respondents	Percentage
1	Married	28	70
2	Divorce	5	12.5
3	Widow	7	17.5
	Total	40	100

Source Based on field survey

The table no 1.6 show that ,70 percent respondent married ,12.5 percent respondent divorce,remaining 17.5 percent respondent were widow

Income

To understand the monthly income of the respondents, three categories of income have been given to the respondents. The data regarding the total monthly family income of the respondents' family were collected and are presented in the table no.1.7 below.

Table-1.7 Income Groups of respondents

Sr,no	Income group	No. Of respondents	Percentage
1	Below 5000	32	80
2	5000-8000	07	17.5
3	8000-10000	01	2.5
	Total	40	100

Source Based on field survey

In this table-1,8 analysis that various steps of income groups, no. of members and per cent of different income groups. So first group bellow 5000 Rs, in 32 members of 80 per cent, second group 5000-8000 Rs in 7 members of 17.5. per cent, and third group 8000-10,000 Rs in 1 members of 2.5per

cent and overall 40 members sampling in Dighanchi village.

Numbers of hours in the field

The data regarding the number of hours these female agricultural labourers work in the field were collected in the present study and presented in the table no. 2.2 below.

Table no1.9. Total Number of Hours they Work in the Field

Sr.no	Numbers of hours working	Respondents	Percentage
1	6	30	75
2	8	10	25
	Total	40	100

Source Based on field survey

The table no0 1.9 indicates that, an overwhelming majority of the respondents 75 percent opined that they work hours a day in the field and only 25 percent of the respondents opined that they work atleast 8 hours a day in the field. It is clearly revealed in the present study that these female

labourers have to work minimum 6 hours and maximum 8 hours in the feild

Wage payment mode

The data regarding the wage payment mode of female agricultural labours get, a question asked was, how frequently do you get your wages? The responses given by the respondents are presented in the table no.1.10 below.

Tabale 1.10 Wage payment method

Sr.no	Wage payment method	Respondent	Percentage
1	Daily	2	5
2	Once in week	38	95
3	Once in 15 days	-	-
4	Once in month	-	-
	Total	40	100

Source Based on field survey

It can be seen from the data presented in the table no.1.10 that, majority of the respondents 5 percent receives wages daily, another 95 percent of respondents receives wages once in a week, the number of respondents who receives wages daily and once in a month was found to be insignificant

A question was asked to the respondents about the health problems they are facing due to the nature of their work. The responses collected were presented in the table no.2.5 below. The data presented in the table no. 2.5 revealed that, a majority 90 percent of the respondents opined that they are facing any health problems due their nature of work but 10 percent of the respondents opined that they are not facing health problems due to nature of their work.

Health problems

Table no.1.11.any health problem due to work

Sr.no	Health problems	Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	36	90
2	No	4	10
	Total	40	100

Source Based on field survey

Findings

Majority of women respondents 62.5 percentage found the sc categories Due to their economic backwardness these people are landless and found to

be engaged in the labour activity .the majority of respondent found to belong to 90 percent hindu religion of the present study. It clearly reveals that overwhelming majority (79 percent Illiterate, up to 7th) of the respondents found to be less educated or illiterate which forced him to do agricultural work

where no skill is required. It is clearly indicated in the present study that respondents belong to both joint and nuclear family structure. It clearly reveals that married women (70 percent) are freely engaged in the agricultural activity as a labour force as compared to divorced or widow women. Majority of the respondents (80 percent) selected in the sample could be said to belong to Rs.5000 income groups against this background. It means they are economically poor. It is clearly revealed in the present study that these female labourers have to work minimum 6 hours a day in the field. It clearly revealed that 90% of female agricultural labourers face some health problems due to the kind of work they do. Wage payment mode majority 90 percent respondent receive one week their wage majority of them get it once in a week.

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